

Histomorphological Spectrum of Skin Adnexal Tumours – A Hospital Based Study**Phalgune Priyadarshini¹, Goutami Das Nayak², Ranjan Kumar Mallick³, Gouranga Charan Prusty⁴, Kalyani Prava Gouda⁵, Lity Mohanty⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack⁵Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack⁶Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack

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Abstract:

Adnexal tumours of skin originate from the pluripotent stem cells and they can be classified into four groups based on their differentiation towards hair follicles, sebaceous glands, apocrine glands or eccrine glands. Due to their diversity in clinical presentation, it's a diagnostic challenge for clinicians and pathologists to give an accurate final diagnosis. Histopathology is the gold standard and along with immunohistochemistry in some cases helps in reaching the conclusive diagnosis.

Keywords: Adnexal, Eccrine, Apocrine, Immunohistochemistry.

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Introduction

Skin is the largest organ of body which is made up of epidermis, dermis and skin adnexa giving rise to a variety of neoplasms. Adnexal tumours of skin originate from the pluripotent stem cells, which differentiate along multiple different pathways. This explains how adnexal lesions simulate their mature counterparts and various histological features often coexist within the same tumor. [1] Adnexal tumours can be classified into four groups based on their differentiation towards hair follicles, sebaceous glands, apocrine glands or eccrine glands [2].

Skin appendageal tumours also constitute a part of certain genetic syndromes like Muir-Torre syndrome & Cowden syndrome. [3] As majority of skin adnexal tumours have a similar clinical presentation, it's a diagnostic challenge for clinicians and pathologists to give an accurate final diagnosis. A complete meticulous history and clinical examination is essential. [4] Histopathology is the gold standard and along with immunohistochemistry in some cases helps in reaching the conclusive diagnosis. [5]

Aim of the Study

To study the histopathological spectrum of skin adnexal tumours.

Material and Method

A retrospective study was carried out in the department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, and Cuttack constituting all skin adnexal tumours between January 2022 to December 2023. The study was done All newly diagnosed primary cases of skin adnexal tumors received in the histopathology department were included in the study. Cases of adnexal tumours already undergoing treatment were excluded. Ethical clearance was obtained from institutional ethical committee (IEC number- 1736/24.07.24). Samples were received fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin along with relevant clinical details like name, age, gender, anatomical site and family history. Grossing and tissue processing was done. Paraffin embedded blocks were prepared and stained by routine Haematoxylin & eosin stains. The stained sections were studied under light microscope and histopathological findings were noted by two independent pathologists. Whenever required, special stains and immunohistochemistry were done. The final diagnosis was given and the tumours were categorized according to WHO classification of skin tumours, 2022. Since the study was retrospective and descriptive, individual parameters were not comparable to obtain a statistical significance.

Data was analysed using Microsoft Excel 2014 version and results were expressed in percentage.

Results

A total of 56 cases were diagnosed as skin adnexal tumours. There were 2 malignant cases, while rest were benign. The age range of patients varied from 5 years to 70 years. Most common age group affected was 31-40 years (23.2%) while least common age group was 61-70 yrs (5.3%) (Table/Fig.1). There were 29 males (51.8%) and 27

females (48.2%) in the study with male: female ratio being 1.07:1. (Table/Fig.2) Head and neck was the most common anatomical site (23/56, 41.07%) while abdomen (2/56, 3.5%) was the least common. (Table/Fig.2). Most of the tumours were benign (54/56, 96.4%). Hair follicle tumours were most common (27, 48.2%) followed by sweat gland tumours (14.25%) (Table/Fig.4). There were only two malignant tumours (3.6%) - malignant nodular hidradenoma (Table/Fig 8c, d) and sebaceous carcinoma (Table/Fig9b)

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age Group	Number Of Cases(N)	Percentage (%)
0-10	5	8.9
11-20	9	16.1
21-30	11	19.6
31-40	13	23.2
41-50	10	17.86
51-60	5	8.9
61-70	3	5.3
TOTAL	56	100

Table 2: Gender Distribution

Gender	Number Of Cases(N)	Percentage (%)
Males	29	51.78
Females	27	48.22
Total	56	100

Table 3: Site Distribution

Site Of Tumour	Number Of Cases(N)	Percentage (%)
Head & neck	23	41.07
Upper extremity	11	19.64
Lower extremity	9	16.07
Chest	4	7.14
Back	7	12.5
Abdomen	2	3.57
Total	56	100

Table 4: Tumour Differentiation

Tumour Differentiation	Number Of Cases(N)	Percentage (%)
Eccrine	14	25
Follicular/Pilar	27	48.21
Sebaceous	12	21.42
Apocrine	3	5.35
Total	56	100

Table 5: Tumour Differentiation and Gender Distribution

Appendageal Tumours	Male	Female	Total
ECCRINE(14)			
Eccrineporoma	1	1	2
Nodular hidradenoma	3	5	8
Malignant hidradenoma	1	0	1
Chondroidsyringoma	2	1	3
PILAR(27)			
Trichilemmal cyst	7	9	16
Pilomatricoma	6	4	10
Trichoepithelioma	0	1	1

Sebaceous(12)			
Nevus sebaceous of Jadahson	4	3	7
Sebaceous hyperplasia	1	1	2
Sebaceous adenoma	2	0	2
Sebaceous carcinoma	0	1	1
APOCRINE(3)			
Apocrine adenoma	2	0	2
Syringocysadenomapapillefrum	0	1	1
Total	29	27	56

Tumours with follicular differentiation were most common (48.2%). Among these, trichilemmal cyst was the most common (28.57%), followed by Pilomatrixoma (Table/Fig.6a) comprising 17.86%.

Eccrine differentiation was seen in 25% of cases. Among the benign tumors, nodular hidradenoma (Table/Fig.6b) was the most common (14.28%), followed by chondroid syringoma (16.6%) eccrine poroma (3.57%) (Table/Fig.7). There was only one malignancy in this category which was a case of malignant nodular hidradenoma (1.78%). This case was diagnosed a malignant adnexal tumour (Table/Fig.8a,b), possibly malignant hidradenoma. P40 showed negative staining in tumour cells while EMA

(epithelial membrane antigen) showed strong cytoplasmic positivity in >90% tumour cells thus confirming diagnosis of malignant hidradenoma (Table/Fig.8c,d). Sebaceous differentiation was noted in 15.3% of cases, commonest being Nevus sebaceous of Jadahson seen in 12.5% cases, followed by sebaceous hyperplasia and sebaceous adenoma (Table/Fig.9a), each constituting 3.57%. There was a malignant case of sebaceous carcinoma (1.78%) (Table/Fig.9b)

Apocrine differentiation was the least common type in the study seen in 5.3% of cases. There were 2 cases of apocrine adenoma (Table/Fig.10) and a single case of syringocystadenoma papilliferum.

[Table/Fig.6]: a) Pilomatrixoma showing islands of basaloid cells with interspersed shadow cells (H&E, 100x) b) Nodular hidradenoma having solid and cystic areas with polyhedral cells and clear cells; tubular lumina lined by columnar or cuboidal secretory cells (H&E 400x).

[Table/Fig 7]: Eccrine Poroma comprising of monomorphic cuboidal cells having deep basophilic nuclei.(H&E,400x)

[Table/Fig.8: a) Malignant adnexal tumour with high cellularity and pleomorphism (H&E,100x) b) Same tumour at higher resolution showing nuclear atypia, prominent nucleoli and mitotic figures(H&E, 400x) c) Negative staining of tumour cells for p40 ruling out squamous cell carcinoma(IHC, 400x) d) Positive cytoplasmic staining for EMA in>90% tumour cells confirming it to be malignant adnexal tumour, possibly malignant nodular hidradenoma(IHC 400x)

[Table/Fig-9]: a) Sebaceous adenoma displaying a well circumscribed lobulated tumour with mixture of basaloid cells and mature adipocytes (H&E,100x) b)Sebaceous carcinoma with mature appearing sebocytes and few atypical basaloid cells. Mild pleomorphism seen; mitotic figures noted (H&E,400x)

Table/Fig.10: Apocrine adenoma: Dermal tumour with tubules lined by bilayered epithelium separated by fibrous stroma. Cystic dilatation and apocrine snouts also noted. (100x)

Discussion

Incidence and prevalence of skin adnexal tumors in Indian population is variable. The study conducted by K Kamyab Hesari et al, [6] reported a prevalence rate of 3.3% while a study conducted by Kaur K et al, [7] showed a prevalence rate of 0.3%. The most commonly affected age group was 31-40years in present study (Table-1). Kaur et al [7] found age group 20-39 years to be most commonly affected. However, 51–60 years age group was the most common to be involved in study by Sharma et al. [10] present study showed higher predilection of skin adnexal tumors in males (51.78%) as compared to females (48.21%) with male: female ratio being 1.07:1(Table-2). Ankit S et al [10] found male to female ratio as 1.07:01. Similar observations were noted by Kaur K et al [7] & Kala PS et al [8]. On the contrary, a female predominance was observed with male: female ratio of 1:1.6 by Gayathree et al [11]. Head and neck [41.07%] was the most common site of distribution of adnexal tumours followed by upper extremities (19.64%) (Table-3). The least common site affected site was abdomen (3.57%). Kaur K et

al [9], El Ochi et al [12] and Sharma et al[10] had similar findings. 96.42% (54/56) tumors were benign while 3.57% (2/56) cases were malignant. The 2 malignant cases were malignant hidradenoma (Fig) and sebaceous carcinoma (Fig). These findings were similar to studies of Kala et al [8], Kaur et al [7] and Radhika et al. [9] Most of the adnexal tumours in present study had follicular differentiation (48.21%) cases followed by tumors with eccrine gland differentiation (25%) followed by sebaceous tumors (21.43%), while tumours with apocrine gland differentiation was least common (Table-5). Trichilemmal cyst (28.6%) was the most common entity among all adnexal tumours of skin (Table-5) Pilar differentiation was most common in studies by El Ochi et al [12], Kaur et al [9] and Kala et al[8]. Studies by Sharma et al [10] and Gayathri et al [11] found eccrine tumours to be the most common.

Immunohistochemistry has limited role in diagnosis of skin adnexal tumours, but certain markers prove useful to distinguish malignant adnexal tumors from their benign counterparts.

Table/Fig.11: Comparative Studies by Other Authors

Study	Kaur et al	Kala et al	Radhika et al	Sharma et al	Gayathree et al	El Ochi et al	Present study
No of cases	110	64	35	56	29	96	56
Most common age grp	20-39	30-40	20-30	51-60	30-40	31-40	21-30
Sex ratio	1.03:1	1:1.29	0.7:1	1.07:1	1:1.6	1.7:1	1.07:1
Most common site	Head & neck	Head & neck	Head & neck	Head & neck	Face	Head & neck	Head & neck
Most common tumour	Pilomatricoma	Pilomatricoma	Nevus sebaceous of Jadassohn	Nodular hidradenoma	Eccrine poroma	Pilomatricoma	Trichilemmal cyst

Conclusion

Adnexal tumors of skin are quite distinct with characteristic histopathological features.

They are commonly distributed in the head, neck and trunk. Due to their variable and overlapping clinical presentation, they pose a diagnostic challenge to clinicians.

Histopathology with the help of immunohistochemistry helps in reaching the final correct diagnosis.

Also, it's important to note that malignant adnexal tumours, though rare can occur and they need to be differentiated from their benign counterparts as well as from other cutaneous malignancies due malignant features therapeutic and prognostic implications.

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